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Title: Transitions to Lone Motherhood and Practices of Resistance: Early Findings from a Study in Four European Countries

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Abstract

The Study on TRansition and Exclusion in Society of Single-Mums (STRESSMums) adopts the sociological approach of Institutional Ethnography (IE) and it collects data in Belgium, Italy, Spain, and in the UK through discursive interviews to lone mothers, judicial professionals, and gender issues activists, participant observations, and photo-voice sessions involving mothers and professionals.

The interest of the research study is about the lone mothers' everyday strategies and social practices to claim inclusion and to negotiate or not negotiate, on the one hand, the dominant definition of family and parenthood proposed by institutions and professionals, and, on the other hand, the less legitimated and multiple situated definitions proposed by lone parents and embodied by their families. The analysis takes into consideration the transition from double parenthood to lone motherhood, in particular paying attention to the period of judicial evaluation for child custody and judicial decisions for allowances and other obligations. This paper presents the early findings of this research study; in particular, it considers the interviews involving single mothers as participants. Beginning from the mothers' standpoint, the paper analyses the mothers' specific modes of knowledge to coordinate their

actions during that period of transition and evaluation. It discusses the text-mediated discursive practices that define family and parenthood as embodied know-how and perception, the ruling relations that shape the local experiences of mothers' everyday lives, and their forms and practices of resistance to the normatively organized conception of family.

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Introduction and description of the research study

The purpose of this conference paper is to bring you up to date with the latest findings of my current research project which is a two-year IE on the legal transition from double to single parenthood in four European countries (Belgium, Italy, Spain, and the UK).

The objectives of the study are to analyze texts, processes, and discourses that organize the courts' evaluations on children's custody and the strategies of professionals and lone mothers (Tartari 2019). STRESSMums project adopts the sociological approach of Institutional Ethnography (IE) (Smith 2005; 2006).

The research starts analyzing the standpoint of the lone mothers through in-depth interviews.

Then, the research study involves legal professionals, gender activists, and other professionals like social workers, asking them to explain how they read and interpret the legal texts (like the law on children's custody) translating them in a language that fits the needs of their clients, the mothers.

The analysis aims to understand how texts' interpretations, translations, and discourses shape the everyday life of mothers during that legal transition.

The methodological approach of this research focuses on three aspects that are analyzed (see also: Murray 2020).

The first aspect concerns the *texts*: mainly the law on shared custody and other texts that rule that legal transition. The second aspect considers the *process*: that is, the active translation of the law by professionals (“readers”) that organize the evaluations about children custody. This process is taken into consideration with a particular focus on the agency of the readers and how they explain the text to “non-readers” (i.e., the mothers). The third and last aspect concerns the *discourse*: the textually mediated discourse that circulates among professionals (“readers”) and mothers (“non-readers”) and that rules mothers’ everyday life. This discourse is analyzed to highlight specific mythologies and ideological codes.

Early findings

To respond to the organizers’ request for the session organized by the Working Group 06 on Institutional Ethnography for the IV ISA Forum of Sociology, I will briefly present some of the early findings of my study.

First, I will focus on what I have found and why I think it matters. To start with, I’d like to show a fragment from an interview that I collected during the Belgian fieldwork from a mother about her legal transition to single parenthood. She said:

“...she [my daughter] was so young at the time we split and he [her ex-partner] has not seen her for several months and I read a book that was suggested to me by the lawyer. It was a book, *she [the lawyer] said*, that also in court the opinions are based upon. So, I went through the book...

And also if they [children] haven't seen one of both parents for a long time, it might be interesting to do it *in a progressive mode*. So, the agreement that was made finally was one with calendars. So like: when she was two years old he would see her during holiday periods for two days. When she's three years old, three days. Four years old, four days. So, it would fill up to a 50/50 during the

holidays when she is about seven years old. Now, practically how it turned out, he can see her on Sunday every month and one Saturday.

[However], he showed up four times, then he didn't show up six times. During the holidays, he actually, the summer holidays, he didn't show up any day. [...]

The title of the book is something like “*A week to mom and a week to dad. What children really need in a divorce.*” I was really thinking: “We need to do it 50/50 because that will be good for our daughter. If we don't split it equally, she will turn into a monster or something else.” But [the lawyer] suggested to me to read [in-depth] that book for other insights about co-parenting, that it doesn't have to be 50/50 in every situation. [...]

And (at the court) he wanted a 50/50 agreement on paper. *On paper!* And then he said: “I will show up whenever I feel like it.” I didn't realize it immediately because I was focused on the calendars. I felt so guilty for my daughter. But when we left, my lawyer said: “Wow, it's so crazy of him to say that to the judge, to ask 50/50, because then he would also get 50% of the child allowance”.

Later, in another part of the interview, this mother began to cry and she explained to me that, as she has been not able to ensure a 50/50 real agreement, every day she is worried about the psychological wellbeing of her daughter.

I would like to underline some ideas which emerged from the fieldwork.

This fragment offers the opportunity to reflect upon the *role of the experts* (in the field of psychology or similar subjects) and *the role of the lawyers*, in Belgium, one of the four countries that my study takes into consideration.

About the experts, we know that during the legal transition to lone parenthood, experts have the role of a translator of psychological texts and ideological codes for “non-readers” like parents.

This fragment describes a common situation of the fieldwork in Belgium: books like that rule mothers' actions.

There is no direct contact, a dialog, a relationship between the expert and the mother. In Belgium, experts are usually not involved in evaluations for courts, unlike in other countries.

Mothers, like the mother of the fragment, read that text as a non-expert reader and they assume that all the statements are correct.

They try to shape their parenthood through those assumptions or *recipes* like the “50-50 child”, “one week-one week child”, or the “rule of the progression mode”.

In the everyday course of actions, they try to convince themselves of the need for the application of those recipes, like something that appears as *rational* and *objective*.

Other interviewees explained that these abstract rules often do not fit the everyday reality of children and mothers. On the other hand, these general “recipes” and rules, like the 50-50 rule, can be used by ex-partners to avoid paying child maintenance. In doing so these recipes shape the future of the children in the opposite direction of their original aim, that is an evident paradox.

Furthermore, I would like to offer some considerations about the lawyers’ role.

Usually, lawyers seem to be focused on the process of translation of legal texts to their clients.

However, sometimes, lawyers support mothers with the interpretation of these specific psychological texts, like in the fragment I showed.

Therefore, mothers highlight the choice of the “right” lawyer as a crucial moment in the phase of transition from double to single parenthood.

The lawyer can be described also as a “*proofreader*”. As these mothers bring many texts to the lawyers, many proofs (“evidence”), they need a reliable lawyer who provides a correct translation and interpretation of those proofs to the court.

Therefore, the most successful situations are described as those situations wherein mothers and lawyers are able to *coordinate* with each other in reading, interpreting, and *proofreading* the texts.

I collected many interviews with very useful examples of coordination, reading, and *proofreading* of texts, for example when the mother and the lawyer work collaboratively on *the draft* of the

petition. In these specific situations, it seems that we can find some forms of resistance against the ideological codes that I showed in the fragment of the interview.

Conclusion

To conclude, I am still drawing on some of these aspects, and how to interpret them. Anyway, the interviews offer very useful indications about the weaknesses of the legal procedures and the law that rule children custody from the mothers' perspective.

As the aim of the study is also contributing to improving these procedures, laws, and policies, I will work on translating them into a report for each of the countries involved in this project.

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References

Murray Ó. M. (2020) Text, process, discourse: doing feminist text analysis in institutional ethnography, *International Journal of Social Research Methodology*, 25:1, 45-57, DOI: 10.1080/13645579.2020.1839162

Smith, D. E. (2005). *Institutional ethnography: A sociology for people*, Lanham: Altamira.

Smith, D. E. (2006). *Institutional Ethnography as Practice*, Lanham: Rowman & Littlefield.

Tartari, M. (2019). *Study on TRansition and Exclusion in Society of Single-Mums (STRESS-Mums)*.

European Commission. Retrieved January 2nd 2020 from //cordis.europa.eu/project/id/843976